

Heated Humidified High Flow Nasal Cannula versus Nasal Continuous Positive Airway Pressure as a Primary Respiratory Support for Mild to Moderate Respiratory Distress Syndrome in Preterm Infants

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Abstract:

Introduction: Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS) is the most common cause for respiratory distress in newborns. Mild to moderate RDS is treated with non-invasive methods. NCPAP is the most commonly used mode of non-invasive mode in RDS but newer modalities like HFNC also an emerging modality with similar efficacy and has a similar morbidity and mortality profile in managing mild to moderate RDS.

Objectives: To compare the efficacy, morbidity & mortality profile of HFNC versus NCPAP as a primary mode of respiratory support for mild to moderate respiratory distress in preterm infants.

Methodology: Hospital based Randomized Controlled Trial was done on eligible neonates with RDS. HFNC was delivered through the short nasal prongs and nasal CPAP was delivered through Hudson's prongs and outcomes of both the methods were compared in terms of efficacy, morbidity and mortality.

Results: Out of 100 newborns, 50 were treated with HFNC and 50 were with NCPAP technique. We found there was no significant difference in the primary outcomes among both the groups. Incidence rate of adverse events did not differ in terms of many among both the modalities, but there was a statistically significant difference in incidence of nasal trauma which was more in NCPAP group. And also there was no significant difference in mortality rate among both the groups.

Conclusion: HFNC technique is feasible, safe and has similar efficacy along with morbidity profile when compared to NCPAP technique. Both HFNC and NCPAP techniques reduce the requirement of mechanical ventilation and need for surfactant instillation.

Keywords: RDS, HFNC, NCPAP, SAS.

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Introduction

Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) is a disease affecting preterm neonates caused by insufficient pulmonary surfactant in alveoli. RDS is caused by insufficient pulmonary surfactant in alveoli. RDS is common in preterm neonates and the main cause of respiratory failure in first 6 hours of life. [1]

The incidence of RDS is inversely proportional to the gestational age. The risk being 60% in less than 28 weeks and 30% between 28 to 34 weeks of gestation. If left untreated, it leads to high mortality; the reported case fatality is 57 to 89% in low- and middle-income countries. [2] Severity of RDS is categorized into mild, moderate and severe based on two scoring systems namely Silverman Anderson Score (SAS) and Downe's Vidyasagar Score. We used Silverman Anderson Score in our study.

There exist multiple methods for the management of respiratory distress syndrome.

Non invasive modalities are helpful in mild to moderate RDS with spontaneously breathing neonates and invasive modalities are needed in severe RDS and in those who fail to improve with non invasive ventilatory modalities. In mild to moderate RDS both Nasal Continuous Positive Airway Pressure (NCPAP) and High Flow Nasal Cannula (HFNC) are used; both has advantages and disadvantages. But the popularity of High Flow seems to be due to other advantages like, the cannulae are easier to apply than NCPAP prongs, more comfortable for infants, associated with less nasal trauma and may enable easier access to babies faces. Thus allowing greater opportunities for feeding and parental bonding. [33]

In mild to moderate Respiratory distress syndrome non-invasive methods are preferred. With an evolving era HFNC has been recognized as equally effective mode of primary respiratory support in management of RDS in preterm neonate as that of NCPAP. [29]

Materials and Methods

Study Design:

Hospital based Randomized Controlled Trial. Study was planned for 12 months after getting approval by Institutional Ethical committee. Target population include neonates delivered and admitted with mild to moderate RDS in NICU of bal chikitsalaya, RNT medical college, Udaipur, Rajasthan.

All the neonates who have met the inclusion criteria after taking informed consent were randomized into two groups based on computer generated random numbers namely Group A as HFNC and Group B as NCPAP .

All the collected data managed and analysed with standard software of Biostatistics (SPSS version 16.0).

Statistical analysis of the data was done with Chi-square test (for qualitative analysis), Student t-test (for Quantitative data) with assistance of qualified statistician. A P value <0.005 was considered as statistically significant.

Distribution of the Sample

Figure 1: Distribution of the Sample

Results

A total of 600 preterm newborns with RDS were assessed for eligibility during the study period. Out of them 230 newborns with RDS were of gestational age <30 wks and were of severe RDS, 120 newborns with RDS were of gestational age >34 wks, 250 newborns were between 30 to 34 wks, among those 250 newborns 130 newborns

required surfactant therapy and 20 newborns had a major congenital anomalies, and remaining 100 newborns with RDS were included in the study, these were randomized and allotted into two groups namely HFNC and NCPAP.

In HFNC modality, 27 (54%) were male babies and 23(46%) were female babies. In NCPAP modality, 32 (64%) were male babies and 18 (36%) were

female babies. The gestational age in the study group was between 30 to 34 wks. The mean gestational age group in HFNC group was 32.14 ± 1.30 wks (Mean \pm SD) and in NCPAP group 32.16 ± 1.55 wks (Mean \pm SD). The average birth weight in HFNC group was 1537 ± 244 Gms (Mean \pm SD) and in NCPAP group 1446 ± 228 gms (Mean \pm SD). Antenatal steroids were given to the mothers of all the 100 newborns included in the study. In HFNC group vs NCPAP groups, 46/50 (92%) vs 40/50 (80%) newborn babies born to mothers who had significant illness respectively. In HFNC group, 35 /50(70%) and in NCPAP 40/50 (80%) newborns were weaned off within 72 hrs of administration of the modality and remaining 15/50(30%) babies in HFNC and 10/50(20%) babies in NCPAP fell down under the criteria of treatment failure. There was no statistically significant difference in the primary outcome among both the groups (P =0.248, Relative Risk 0.87, 0.6964 to 1.0 at CI 95%). In HFNC modality, 2(6%) newborns and in NCPAP 6(12%) newborns required mechanical ventilation within 72 hrs of therapy. In HFNC group 6(12%) newborns required surfactant instillation.

In NCPAP group, 8 (16%) newborns required surfactant instillation in the early period of the treatment. Before administration of modality, all the 100 newborns with RDS were having SAS between 4 - 6 and after reaching primary outcome of HFNC modality, 35 (70%) newborn babies had a SAS score of less than 4, and remaining 15 (35 %) newborns had SAS score ≥ 7 . In NCPAP group 40 (80%) newborn babies had a SAS score of less than 4, and remaining 10 (20 %) newborns had SAS score ≥ 7 . The arterial PH, PCO₂, PO₂ and NaHCO₃ in HFNC group (Mean \pm SD) before oxygen administration were 7.28 ± 0.12 , 39.66 ± 11.7 , 85.3 ± 24.52 and 21.12 ± 2.86 respectively and at the time of weaning / Failure of the therapy, the arterial PH, PCO₂, PO₂ and NaHCO₃ are 7.31 ± 0.15 , 42.68 ± 10.91 , 87.82 ± 29.52 and 22.62 ± 3.26 respectively. The arterial PH, PCO₂, PO₂ and NaHCO₃ in NCPAP group (Mean \pm SD) before oxygen administration were 7.27 ± 0.11 , 39.9 ± 10.89 , 83.74 ± 25.7 and 21.33 ± 2.11 respectively and at the time of weaning / failure of the modality, the

arterial PH, PCO₂, PO₂ and NaHCO₃ were 7.30 ± 0.13 , 42.56 ± 9.9 , 83.28 ± 26.98 and 22.08 ± 2.3 respectively. The average duration of HFNC requirement for weaning off of the babies was 29.04 ± 13.35 (Mean \pm SD) hrs and in NCPAP group was 31.2 ± 17.014 (Mean \pm SD) hrs. The average total duration of oxygen requirement including nasal prongs and oxygen hood in HFNC group was 60 ± 30 hrs (Mean \pm SD) and in NCPAP group was 58.32 ± 34.45 hrs (Mean \pm SD). Out of 50 newborns treated with HFNC modality, 9 (18%) newborns had apnoea, 4(8%) newborns had shock ,10(20%) newborns had bradycardia, 3(6%) newborns had abdominal distension, 13(26%) newborns had sepsis/ NEC, 1(2%) newborn had pulmonary hemorrhage and none among them had a nasal trauma, pneumothorax, and intracranial hemorrhage. Out of 50 newborns treated with NCPAP modality , 6 (12%) newborns had apnoea, 6(12%) newborns had shock ,10(20%) babies had bradycardia , 6(12%) of them had a nasal trauma, 8(16%) newborns had abdominal distension, 21(42%) newborns had sepsis/NEC ,3(6%) newborns had pulmonary hemorrhage and none among them had pneumothorax and intracranial hemorrhage . Incidence of adverse events didn't differ in terms of apnoea (p =0.401), shock (p=0.505), bradycardia (p=1), abdominal distension (p=0.603), NEC/ sepsis, pulmonary haemorrhage, and pneumothorax among both the study groups (p>0.05). But there was a statistically significant difference in incidence of nasal trauma which was more in nasal CPAP group as p value was less than 0.05 (p=0.012).

Average duration of hospital stay among newborns treated with HFNC modality was 13.1 ± 3.49 (Mean \pm SD) days and in NCPAP modality was 14.38 ± 4.55 (Mean \pm SD) days. Among 50 newborns treated with HFNC modality, 2 (4%) babies expired and 48 (96%) babies got discharged successfully and 50 newborns treated with NCPAP modality, 2 (4%) babies expired and 48 (96%) babies got discharged successfully. Mortality was similar among both the groups. In this study, there was no statistically significant difference in the incidence of mortality among both the groups as p value was 1, Relative Risk 1, 0.9231 to 1.08 at CI 95%.

Table 1:

Baseline Characters	HFNC (n =50)	NCPAP (n = 50)	P Value
Gender			
Male	27(54%)	32(64%)	0.309
Female	23(46%)	18(36%)	
Gestational age			
30 – 32 wks	35(70%)	33(66%)	0.668
32 – 34 wks	15(30%)	17(34%)	
Average Birth weight (gms) (Mean+SD)	1537 ± 244	1446 ± 228	0.058
Antenatal steroids	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	1.0
Maternal illness	46 (92%)	40(80%)	0.084

Primary outcome (Wean off)	35(70%)	40(80%)	0.248
Need for mechanical ventilation	2(4%)	6(12%)	0.140
Need for surfactant instillation	6(12%)	8(16%)	0.59
Average duration of modality requirement in hrs (Mean+SD)	29.04 ± 13.35	31.2 ± 17.014	0.482
Total duration of o2 (Nasal prongs & hood) hrs (Mean+SD)	60 ± 30.51	58.32± 34.45	0.799

Table 2:

Complications	HFNC (n=50)	NCPAP (n = 50)	P Value
Apnoea	9(18%)	6(12%)	0.401
Shock	4(8%)	6(12%)	0.505
Bradycardia	10(20%)	10(20%)	1.0
Nasal trauma	0	6(12%)	0.012
Abdominal distension	3(6%)	8(16%)	0.603
Pneumothorax	0	0	0
Sepsis/NEC	13(26%)	21(42%)	0.091
Pulmonary hemorrhage	1(2%)	3(6%)	0.307
Duration of hospital stay (days) (Mean + SD)	13.1 ± 3.49	14.38 ± 4.55	0.118
Mortality	2 (4%)	2(4%)	1.0

Figure 2: Distribution according to the primary outcome of the procedure

Figure 3: Distribution of adverse events and complications among different modalities.

Discussion

In this prospective observational study, we found no significant difference in the intubation and MV within 72 hours of initiating support between HFNC and NCPAP as a primary mode of respiratory support. Though the rate of weaning was higher in NCPAP group, there was no statistically significant difference among the two groups so far as weaning was considered. ($P = 0.248$, Relative Risk 0.87, 0.6964 to 1.0 at 95% CI). Jeonghee Shin et al [45] observed that 16 of 42 infants randomized to HHHFNC showed treatment failure compared to 9 of 43 infants using nCPAP (Risk difference 17.17 [-1.90-36.23]; $P = 0.099$). Bradley A. Yoder et al [46] observed that there were no difference in early failure for HHHFNC (23/212 [10.8%]) versus nCPAP (18/220 [8.2%]; $P = .344$), subsequent need for any intubation (32/212 [15.1%] vs 25/220 [11.4%]; $P = .252$) respectively. Study conducted by Deeparaj Hegde et al [44] shown that out of 88 preterm infants enrolled in the

study, 42 received NCPAP and 46 received HHHFNC. Treatment failure rate in HHHFNC group was 19.5% and the failure rate in NCPAP group was 26.2% ($P=0.46$). There was no statistically significant difference in apnoea ($p = 0.401$), shock ($p=0.505$), bradycardia ($p=1$), and abdominal distension ($p=0.603$) among the two groups. In the present study, there was no statistical significant differences in NEC/sepsis, pulmonary haemorrhage, and pneumothorax among both the study groups ($p>0.05$). But there was a statistically significant difference in incidence of nasal trauma which was more in NCPAP group as p value was less than 0.05 ($p=0.012$).

Similar results were obtained in a study conducted by Pravesh kumar Sharma et al [41], the overall incidence of nasal trauma was more in NCPAP group in comparison to HHHFNC group. About 34.9% of infants in NCPAP group and 11.4% of infants in HHHFNC group had some form of nasal trauma respectively. The difference among the two

groups was statistically significant as the p value was <0.05 ($P = 0.019$). Incidences of other complications such as apnoea, bradycardia, and air leaks were similar in both groups. The results of our study were in agreement with the study conducted by Deeparaj Hegde et al [41] on 88 preterm infants with RDS in 2016, observed that the incidence of moderate to severe nasal trauma was found in 5 (11%) babies in HFNC group and 17 (41%) babies in NCPAP group, and also observed that 19/46(41%) and 14/42(33%) babies had sepsis in HFNC and NCPAP groups respectively.

None of the infants in either group developed Pneumothorax. They found statistically significant difference between the two groups as p value was <0.05 (p value is 0.01). Again secondary outcomes were similar to that of current study in a study conducted by Gamze Demirel et al [26]. They observed that there was no difference between the groups in the aspects of secondary outcomes such as duration of non-invasive respiratory support and oxygen treatment, maximum FiO_2 level, length of hospital stay, intubation rate, and rates of respiratory distress syndrome, pneumothorax, and bronchopulmonary dysplasia.

In our study, there was no statistically significant difference in mortality between two groups [2(4%) in HFNC vs 2 (4%) in NCPAP] as p value was 1.0, 0.9231 to 1.0 at CI 95%. Deeparaj Hegde et al [44] found that there was no statistically significant difference in the incidence of death between two groups (6/46(13%) in HFNC vs 6/42(14%) in CPAP) respectively. [$P=0.86$]. Tahereh Esmailnia Shirvani et al [38] showed there was no statistically significant difference in the incidence of death between two groups. Odds ratio was found to be 0.556(0.120- 2.569) in HFNC vs 1 in CPAP [$P = 0.452$].

Conclusion

Our study shows that HFNC modality of oxygen administration is as feasible, safe and effective method as that of NCPAP modality to treat the spontaneously breathing neonate with mild to moderate RDS.

HFNC modality of oxygen administration has similar efficacy and morbidity profile such as time required for weaning off, duration of oxygen requirement, need for mechanical ventilation, need for surfactant instillation and duration of hospital stay when compared to NCPAP modality.

HFNC and NCPAP modalities have equal incidence of adverse events except nasal trauma which was more in NCPAP group. Both HFNC and NCPAP modalities reduce the mortality associated with RDS. HFNC modality is as effective as

NCPAP modality in improving the outcomes of RDS management.

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